

Assessment of Sleep Deprivation and Patient Care Abilities among Staff Nurses at a Tertiary Care Hospital, Jammu and Kashmir

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ABSTRACT

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Background

Sleep deprivation among staff nurses, characterized by insufficient sleep of less than 7-9 hours per night, can adversely affect their patient care abilities. This study aimed to assess the level of sleep deprivation among staff nurses, evaluate their patient care abilities, determine the correlation between sleep deprivation and patient care abilities, and identify associations between sleep deprivation/patient care abilities and selected demographic variables.

Objectives

The study employed a quantitative research approach with a descriptive correlational design. A total of 60 staff nurses from ICU, Post-Operative Ward, and Emergency Wards of SKIMS Soura were selected using non-probability purposive sampling. Sleep deprivation was assessed using a self-constructed Sleep Deprivation Checklist, while patient care abilities were evaluated using a Patient Care Ability Rating Scale.

Results

The results revealed that the majority of staff nurses experienced moderate sleep deprivation, while most exhibited good patient care abilities. A negative correlation was found between sleep deprivation and patient care abilities, indicating that as sleep deprivation increased, patient care abilities decreased. Furthermore, significant associations were found between sleep deprivation and working hours during night duty, as well as between gender and working hours with patient care ability. Based on these findings, it is evident that interventions are needed to address sleep deprivation among staff nurses. Strategies to prevent sleep deprivation should be improved to ensure better patient outcomes. Additionally, efforts should be made to enhance the quality and duration of sleep for staff nurses, such as providing opportunities to nap during night duty or ensuring sufficient staffing during night shifts. These measures are crucial for promoting better patient care and overall well-being among staff nurses.

KEYWORD: Sleep deprivation, Correlation, Patient care ability, Mild, moderate, and severe Sleep deprivation, Good, average and Poor patient care ability.

INTRODUCTION

Nursing is a multifaceted profession that encompasses both art and science, requiring a compassionate heart and a knowledgeable mind. At its core, nursing upholds the values of human dignity and intuitively responds to the needs of patients. This intuition is further strengthened by rigorous education and training, given the diverse specializations and complex skills within the nursing

field. Nurses provide holistic care to individuals of all ages and cultural backgrounds, addressing their physical, emotional, psychological, intellectual, social, and spiritual needs. The nursing profession combines principles from physical and social sciences, nursing theory, and technological advancements to provide comprehensive care to the sick. However, nurses often face challenges in their work, such as exposure to infections and toxic substances,

disruption of circadian rhythms due to night shifts, and the constant fear of contracting diseases in an era of rising resistance.

One significant challenge that nurses encounter is sleep deprivation. Adequate sleep is a biological necessity, essential for maintaining overall health and well-being. On average, adults require 7-8 hours of sleep each night to function optimally. Unfortunately, many individuals, including nurses, fail to meet this requirement, leading to various health problems. Sleep deprivation can result in forgetfulness, weakened immune system, mood swings, depression, and a decline in cognitive function. As nurses grow older and face the demands of shift work, sleep deprivation becomes an even greater concern. Sleep deprivation has severe consequences for the health and performance of nurses. It increases the risk of obesity, diabetes, gastrointestinal disorders, cardiovascular diseases, and certain types of cancer, such as breast and colorectal cancer. Impaired alertness and decreased task performance can lead to errors in patient care and increase the likelihood of traffic accidents. Sleep-deprived nurses also experience excessive daytime sleepiness, which can significantly impact their ability to provide appropriate patient care.

The provision of patient care requires a range of skills and abilities from nurses. Physical care involves attending to basic nursing care, symptom management, and treatment, while comfort measures aim to soothe and relieve patients' physical and mental distress. Psychological care involves effective communication, counseling, and reducing anxiety and fear in patients. Socio-spiritual care encompasses understanding patients' beliefs, advocating for their needs, and coordinating with their families.

Shift work, a common practice in nursing disrupts circadian rhythms and further exacerbates sleep deprivation. Nurses often work long shifts, extending up to 12-18 hours, and may experience unexpected overtime due to patient care responsibilities. Limited sleep time between shifts, combined with commuting and domestic duties, further restricts nurses' ability to obtain adequate rest. Fatigue among nurses increases the risk of critical errors in medication administration and clinical decision-making, compromising patient safety and care quality. Sleep loss not only affects cognitive performance but also impairs physical health. Prolonged sleep deprivation increases the risk of chronic conditions such as diabetes and heart disease. It also hampers the immune system's ability to function effectively, leaving individuals vulnerable to various illnesses. Furthermore, sleep deprivation can negatively impact mental health, leading to mood swings, decreased creativity, and compromised decision-making abilities.

Nurses face numerous stressors in their profession, and sleep plays a vital role in managing stress. However, studies have shown that a significant percentage of nurses work over 40 hours per week and get less than six hours of sleep per night. Falling asleep on the job is not uncommon, particularly during night shifts. Objective recordings have confirmed that nurses, air traffic controllers, and truck drivers frequently experience brief periods of sleep during their night shifts.

In conclusion, nursing encompasses both an art and a science, demanding both compassion and knowledge from its practitioners. However, the profession is not without its challenges, and sleep deprivation stands out as a significant concern for nurses. Adequate sleep is essential for maintaining physical and mental health, as well as providing safe and effective patient care. Addressing the issue of sleep deprivation among nurses is crucial for ensuring their well-being and the quality of care they provide to patients.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research approach with a descriptive correlational design. Prior permission was obtained from the relevant authorities at Mader-e-Meharban Institute of Nursing Sciences and Research (MMINSR), SKIMS, Soura, Srinagar to conduct the study. Ethical clearance was also obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) at SKIMS. Additionally, permission was granted by the Medical Superintendent and the Heads of the Anaesthesiology and Critical Care Department, as well as the Emergency Medicine Department, to carry out the study on 60 Staff Nurses who were directly involved in bedside nursing care and performing shift duties. Informed consent was obtained from each staff nurse individually before including them as participants in the study, ensuring privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity.

Following the necessary permissions, data collection took place from 10th May to 10th June 2022, involving 60 staff nurses working in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Post-Operative Ward, and Emergency Ward at SKIMS. The demographic data of the participants were assessed through a 10-item questionnaire, covering information such as age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, years of working experience, area of posting, working hours, number of night duties per week, number of patients assigned per nurse, and the chance to have a nap during night duty. Sleep deprivation was assessed using a self-constructed checklist consisting of 30 items, with each correct or incorrect response given a score of '1' or '0', respectively. Patient care ability was assessed using a self-constructed rating scale consisting of 30 items, utilizing a 3-point Likert scale (Always = 2, Sometimes = 1, Never = 0).

The sleep deprivation scores were categorized into three levels based on the criteria established by Amrita Ghimrie, Subrahmaya Nayak, and Maya VK in their 2018 study: mild sleep deprivation (score: 0-10), moderate sleep deprivation (score: 11-20), and severe sleep deprivation (score: 21-30).

The patient care ability scores were categorized into three levels: average (score: 0-20), poor (score: 21-40), and good (score: 41-60).

To ensure content validity, the self-constructed sleep deprivation checklist, and patient care ability rating scale, along with the study objectives, scoring key, content validity certificate, and evaluation criteria, were reviewed by 10 research experts and clinicians specializing in the relevant field. Their suggestions and recommendations were incorporated, leading to necessary modifications of the tools.

The reliability of both the self-constructed sleep deprivation checklist and patient care ability rating scale was determined using the split-half method and Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient formula. The calculated reliability coefficient for the tool was $r = 0.86$, indicating a high level of reliability. Both the sleep deprivation checklist and patient care ability rating scale were found to be consistent and reliable for the study

RESULT

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software program was used for data analysis. Frequency distributions were obtained, and descriptive statistics were calculated.

The majority (48.3%) of study subjects were in the age group between 20-30 years, followed by the age group 31-40 years, i.e., 36.7%. The majority of study subjects (65.0%) were female. 55% of study subjects were married, and 51.7% of study subjects had a B.Sc. in nursing, followed by 38.3% with an M.Sc. in nursing. The majority of study subjects (65.0%) had more than 3 years of experience, followed by 25.0% with experience between 1-3 years. 55% of study subjects were from the emergency department, followed by the ICU department, which accounted for 28.3%. 38.3% of study subjects worked between 6-8 hours, followed by 35.0% who worked 8-10 hours. 53.3% of study subjects worked 3 days per week, followed by 26.7% who worked 4 nights per week.

TABLE 1. Distribution of Staff Nurses According to Demographic Variables. (n=60)

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency(f)	Percentage(%)
Age	20-30 years	29	48.3%
	31-40 years	22	36.7%
	41-- 50 years	7	11.7%
	>50 years	2	3.3%
Gender	Male	21	35.0%
	Female	39	65.0%
Marital Status	Unmarried	27	45.0%
	Married	33	55.0%
	Separated	0	0.0%
	Divorced	0	0.0%

80.0% of study subjects were assigned more than 4 patients, while 11.7% had 4 patients assigned. 55% of study subjects had no chance of napping during night duty, while 45% of respondents used to get a nap during night duty, as depicted in Table 1.

Educational Qualification	GNM	6	10.0%
	B.SC Nursing	31	51.7%
	MSC Nursing	23	38.3%
Years of Working Experience	Ph.d Nurs-ing	0	0.0%
	Below 1 year	4	6.7%
	1 year	2	3.3%
	1-3 years	15	25.0%
Area of Posting	More than 3 years	39	65.0%
	ICU	17	28.3%
	Post-op Ward	10	16.7%
Working Hours	Emergency	33	55.0%
	Upto 6 Hours	8	13.3%
	6-8 Hours	23	38.3%
	8-10 Hours	21	35.0%
How many days a week you often do night duty	Above 10 Hours	8	13.3%
	2 days	12	20.0%
	3 days	32	53.3%
	4 days	16	26.7%
Average no. of patients assigned per Nurse	Two	3	5.0%
	Three	2	3.3%
	Four	7	11.7%
	Above four	48	80.0%
Do you get a chance to have nap during Night Duty	Yes	27	45.0%
	No	33	55.0%

Findings related to the level of sleep deprivation among staff nurses: 48% of nurses were suffering from moderate sleep deprivation, 41.7% were suffering from severe sleep deprivation, and 10% had mild sleep deprivation. The mean score was 18.55, the median score was 19, and the standard deviation was 5.312, within a range of 19, with a maximum score of 27 and a minimum score of 8, as depicted in Table 2.

TABLE. 2. Frequency and Percentage distribution of Study Subjects according to Sleep deprivation Level (n=60)

Sleep deprivation level criteria measures	Frequency (f)	Percentage(%)
Severe Sleep Deprivation (21-30)	25	41.7%
Moderate Sleep Deprivation (11-20)	29	48.3%
Mild Sleep Deprivation (0- 10)	6	10.0%
Maximum =30 Minimum =0.	60	100

Findings related to the level of patient care ability among staff nurses: The majority (66.7%) of staff nurses had good patient care ability, 33.3% had average patient care ability, and 0.0% had low patient care ability. The mean, median, and standard deviation of physical, psychological, and social care ability scores of staff nurses were found to be 45.63, 44, and 8.33, respectively, within a range of 30, with a maximum value of 60 and a minimum of 30. The mean percentage result of patient care ability score among staff nurses was found to be 76.06%, as depicted in Table 3.

TABLE.3. Frequency and Percentage distribution of Study Subjects as per Level of Patient Care ability Criteria. (n=60)

Patient care ability criteria measures	Frequency (f)	Percentage(%)
Good Patient Care Ability (41-60)	40	66.7%
Average Patient Care Ability (21-40)	20	33.3%
Low Patient Care Ability (0-20)	0	0.0%
Maximum =60 Minimum =0		
TOTAL	60	100

Findings related to the association of sleep deprivation with demographic variables: The chi-square value showed that there is a significant association between the sleep deprivation score and the demographic variable of working hours ($p=0.015$). The chi-square value showed that there is no significant association between the sleep deprivation score and the demographic variables of age ($p=0.753$), gender ($p=0.559$), marital status ($p=0.965$), educational qualification ($p=0.087$), years of working experience ($p=0.163$), area of posting ($p=0.305$), number of night duties per week ($p=0.065$), number of patients assigned per nurse ($p=0.354$), and nap during night duty ($p=0.810$), as depicted in Table 4.

Findings related to the association of patient care abilities with demographic variables: The chi-square value showed that there is a significant association between the patient care abilities score and the demographic variables of gender ($p=0.022$) and working hours ($p=0.013$). The chi-square value showed that there is no significant association between the patient care ability score and the demographic variables of age ($p=0.355$), marital status ($p=0.582$), educational qualification ($p=0.156$), years of working experience ($p=0.486$), area of posting ($p=0.088$), number of night duties per week ($p=0.544$), number of patients assigned per nurse ($p=0.411$), and nap during night duty ($p=0.582$), as depicted in Table 5.

Findings related to the correlation between sleep deprivation and patient care abilities among staff nurses: The mean of patient care ability was found to be 45.633, with a standard deviation of 8.316. The mean of sleep deprivation was found to be 18.550, with a standard deviation of 5.312. The correlation result was found to be -0.355 , with a table value of 0.254. The p-value was 0.005, as depicted in Table 6 .

TABLE. 4. Showing Association of Demographic Variables with Sleep Deprivation

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA	L E V E L S (n=60)	ASSOCIATION WITH SLEEP DEPRIVATION SCORE							
		SEVERE SLEEP DEPRIVATION	M O D E R - A T E S L E E P D E P R I V A - T I O N	MILD SLEEP DEPRIVATION	Chi Test	P Value	df	Table Value	Result
Age	20-30 years	13	13	3	3.431	0.753	6	12.592	Not Significant
	31-40 years	9	10	3					
	41-- 50 years	3	4	0					
	>50 years	0	2	0					
Gender	Male	10	10	1	1.165	0.559	2	5.991	Not Significant
	Female	15	19	5					
Marital Status	Unmarried	11	13	3	0.071	0.965	2	5.991	Not Significant
	Married	14	16	3					
	Separated	0	0	0					
	Divorced	0	0	0					
Educational Qualification	GNM	2	4	0	8.119	0.087	4	9.488	Not Significant
	B.SC Nursing	10	15	6					
	MSC Nursing	13	10	0					
	Ph.d Nursing	0	0	0					
Years of Working Experience	Below 1 year	3	1	0	9.201	0.163	6	12.592	Not Significant
	1 year	1	1	0					
	1-3 years	3	8	4					
	More than 3 years	18	19	2					
Area of Posting	ICU	6	10	1	4.834	0.305	4	9.488	Not Significant
	Post-op Ward	2	7	1					
	Emergency	17	12	4					
Working Hours	Upto 6 Hours	3	5	0	15.817	0.015	6	12.592	Significant
	6-8 Hours	13	7	3					
	8-10 Hours	7	13	1					
	Above 10 Hours	2	4	2					
How many days a week you often do night duty	2 days	4	8	0	8.859	0.065	4	9.488	Not Significant
	3 days	17	10	5					
	4 days	4	11	1					
Average no. of patients assigned per Nurse	Two	0	3	0	6.656	0.354	6	12.592	Not Significant
	Three	2	0	0					
	Four	2	4	1					
	Above four	21	22	5					
Do you get a chance to have nap during Night Duty	Yes	12	13	2	0.421	0.810	2	5.991	Not Significant
	No	13	16	4					

TABLE. 5. Showing Association of Patient Care ability scores with selected demographic variables. (n=60)

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA	LEVELS (N=60)	ASSOCIATION WITH PATIENT CARE ABILITY SCORE							
		GOOD PA-TIENT CARE ABILITY	AVERAGE PA-TIENT CARE ABILITY	LOW PA-TIENT CARE ABILITY	Chi Test	P Value	df	Table Value	Result
Age	20-30 years	17	12	0	3.244	0.355	3	7.815	Not Significant
	31-40 years	17	5	0					
	41-- 50 years	4	3	0					
	>50 years	2	0	0					
Gender	Male	10	11	0	5.275	0.022	1	3.841	Significant
	Female	30	9	0					
Marital Status	Unmarried	17	10	0	0.303	0.582	1	3.841	Not Significant
	Married	23	10	0					
	Separated	0	0	0					
	Divorced	0	0	0					
Educational Qualification	GNM	5	1	0	3.714	0.156	2	5.991	Not Significant
	B.SC Nursing	23	8	0					
	MSC Nursing	12	11	0					
	Ph.d Nursing	0	0	0					
Years of Working Experience	Below 1 year	3	1	0	2.440	0.486	3	7.815	Not Significant
	1 year	2	0	0					
	1-3 years	8	7	0					
	More than 3 years	27	12	0					
Do you get a chance to have nap during Night Duty	Yes	17	10	0	0.303	0.582	1	3.841	Not Significant
	Yes	12	13	2					
	No	13	16	4					

COUNTINUED. TABLE. 5. Showing Association of Patient Care ability scores with selected demographic variables.

Area of Post-ing	ICU	14	3	0	4.864	0.088	2	5.991	Not Significant
	Post-op Ward	8	2	0					
	Emergency	18	15	0					
Working Hours	Upto 6 Hours	8	0	0	10.811	0.013	3	7.815	Significant
	6-8 Hours	18	5	0					
	8-10 Hours	9	12	0					
	Above 10 Hours	5	3	0					
How many days a week you often do night duty	2 days	9	3	0	1.219	0.544	2	5.991	Not Significant
	3 days	22	10	0					
	4 days	9	7	0					
	Four	4	3	0					
Average no. of patients assigned per Nurse	Two	3	0	0	2.879	0.411	3	7.815	Not Significant
	Three	2	0	0					
	Four	4	3	0					
	Above four	31	17	0					
Do you get a chance to have nap during Night Duty	Yes	17	10	0	0.303	0.582	1	3.841	Not Significant
	No	23	10	0					

TABLE. 6. Showing the Correlation between Sleep deprivation and Patient Care ability among Study Subjects. (n=60)

Pearson's Correlation			Correlation	Table Value	P Value	Result
	Patient Care Ability	Sleep Deprivation	_ 0.355	0.254	0.005	Significant
Mean	45.633	18.550				
S.D.	8.316	5.312				

DISCUSSION

Discussion about demographic variables of Staff Nurses:

The majority (48.3%) of study subjects were in the age group between 20-30 years, followed by the age group 31-40 years, which accounted for 36.7%. The majority of study subjects (65.0%) were female. 55% of the study subjects were married, and 51.7% of them held a B.Sc. in nursing, followed by 38.3% with an M.Sc. in nursing. The majority of study subjects (65.0%) had more than 3 years of experience, while 25.0% had experience between 1-3 years. 55% of the study subjects were from the emergency department, followed by 28.3% from the ICU department. 38.3% of study subjects worked between 6-8 hours, with 35.0% working 8-10 hours. 53.3% of study subjects worked 3 days per week, while 26.7% worked 4 nights per week. 80.0% of study subjects had more than 4 patients assigned to them, while 11.7% had 4 patients assigned. 55% of study subjects had no chance of taking a nap during night duty, while 45% of respondents used to take a nap during night duty.

The present study's findings are supported by a 2018 research conducted by Amrita Ghimrie, Subrahmaya Nayak, and Maya VK at a selected hospital in Mangalore. They aimed to assess the correlation between sleep deprivation and patient care ability among 60 staff nurses. The study revealed that 46.7% of respondents were below the age of 25, followed by 36.7% in the 26-30 age group. 75% of respondents were female, and 53.7% were married. In terms of work hours, 36.7% of nurses worked 7 to 8 hours a day. The Emergency Department had the highest percentage of nurses at 38.3%, followed by the ICU at 35.0%. When it came to night duty, 50.0% reported working 4 days or more per week, while 33.3% worked 3 days a week. Regarding patient assignments, 50.0% stated they usually had 4 or more patients per nurse, while 23.3% had 2 patients. In terms of experience, 53.0% of nurses had 4 or more years, while 16.7% had less than 1 year. During night duty, 39.6% of nurses took a nap, while 45.8% did not. As for qualifications, 55.3% had a B.Sc in Nursing, and 28.9% had an M.Sc.

Discussion of the Findings Based on the Study Objectives:

SECTION 1. Determining the Level of Sleep Deprivation among Staff Nurses at Skims Soura

In this study, it was found that 48.0% of the staff nurses experienced moderate sleep deprivation, 41.7% had severe sleep deprivation, and 10% suffered from mild sleep deprivation. These findings are consistent with a similar study conducted by Amrita Ghimrie, Subrahmaya Nayak, and Maya VK in 2018 at a selected hospital in Mangalore. Their study involved 60 staff nurses and showed that 53.3% experienced moderate sleep deprivation, 23.3% had severe sleep deprivation, and 23.3% suffered from mild sleep deprivation. Another cross-sectional correlational study conducted by Arelene L Johnson Lorena, Jung Kath-

leen C Brown, Michael T Weaver, and Kathy C Richard in 2014 on 289 hospital nurses in Birmingham revealed that 56% of the nurses were sleep deprived.

SECTION 2. Determining the Patient Care Abilities among Nurses at Skims Soura.

In this study, it was found that 66.7% of the staff nurses had good patient care ability skills, while 33.3% had average skills and 0.0% had poor skills. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Amrita Ghimrie, Subrahmaya Nayak, and Maya VK in 2018 at a selected hospital in Mangalore. Their study showed that 70% of the nurses had good patient care ability, 18.3% had average ability, and 11.7% had poor ability.

SECTION 3. Determining the Correlation between Sleep Deprivation and Patient Care Abilities among Staff Nurses.

In this study, a negative correlation was found between sleep deprivation and patient care abilities. The correlation coefficient was -0.355, the table value was 0.254, and the p-value was 0.005. These findings are consistent with a study conducted by Amrita Ghimrie, Subrahmaya Nayak, and Maya VK in 2018 at a selected hospital in Mangalore. Their study showed a correlation coefficient of -0.367 and a p-value of 0.05.

SECTION 4. Determining the Association between Sleep Deprivation and Selected Demographic Variables.

In this study, a significant association was found between working hours during night duty and sleep deprivation. However, no association was observed with age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, area of posting, number of patients assigned per nurse, number of nights per week, years of experience, and chance to nap during night duty. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Ro-Ting Lin, Yu-Ting Lin, Ying-Fang Hsia, and Chin-Chi Kuo in 2016 with 973 nurses in Taiwan. Their results showed that longer working hours were associated with shorter sleep hours, leading to sleep deprivation.

SECTION 5. Determining the Association between Patient Care Abilities and Selected Demographic Variables.

In this study, gender and working hours were found to be associated with patient care abilities, while age, marital status, educational qualification, years of working experience, area of posting, number of nights per week, number of patients assigned per nurse, and nap during night duty showed no association with patient care ability skills. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Son, Lee, and Ko in South Korea. Their cross-sectional descriptive study on 380 nurses showed that working hours and gender were associated with patient safety competencies and adverse nurse outcomes.

Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into the level of sleep deprivation, patient care abilities, and their association with demographic variables among staff nurses.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of sleep deprivation levels in staff nurses revealed that 48.3% of the samples experienced moderate sleep deprivation. These findings highlight the need for improved intervention strategies to prevent sleep deprivation among these study subjects. Sleep deprivation can have detrimental effects on the well-being and performance of nurses, so addressing this issue is crucial. Another assessment conducted on patient care ability levels in staff nurses showed that 66.7% of the samples exhibited good patient care ability. This indicates that a majority of the nurses possess the skills and capabilities required for providing quality patient care. Interestingly, the study found a negative correlation between sleep deprivation and patient care abilities among staff nurses ($r = -0.355$). The findings suggest that as sleep deprivation increases among the nurses, their patient care abilities decrease. Therefore, it is imperative to prioritize quality sleep and sufficient hours of sleep for staff nurses. Implementing measures such as allowing napping during night duty or ensuring adequate staff personnel during night shifts can contribute to improved patient outcomes and care. Furthermore, the study identified a significant association between sleep deprivation and working hours, indicating that longer working hours are linked to increased sleep deprivation. To mitigate exhaustion and fatigue among staff nurses, it is essential to implement strategies that regulate and limit working hours to a reasonable and necessary level.

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